

A STRATEGIC AND STRUCTURAL PERSPECTIVE IN CORPORATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract

Corporate Entrepreneurship has been recognized as a potentially viable means for promoting and sustaining organizational performance, renewal and corporate competitiveness over the past three decades. The entrepreneurial activities help companies to develop new businesses that create revenue streams. Corporate Entrepreneurship activities also enhance a company's success by promoting product and process innovations. Corporate Entrepreneurship is embodying risk taking, pro-activeness and radical product innovations. These Corporate Entrepreneurship activities can improve organizational growth and profitability and, depending on the company's competitive environment, their impact may increase over time. The empirical evidence is compelling that Corporate Entrepreneurship improves company performance by increasing the firm's pro-activeness and willingness to take risks, and by pioneering the development of new products, process and services through enriching its competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION:-

Entrepreneurship is considered to be a vital component in the process of economic growth and development for various reasons. It is a mechanism by which society converts technological information into products and services (Shane & Venkataraman). This type of entrepreneurially driven innovation in products or services and processes is a crucial engine driving the change process in a capitalist society (Schumpeter). Entrepreneurship discovers and mitigates not only technological, but also temporal and spatial inefficiencies in an economy (Shane & Venkataraman). The above makes it clear that the study of entrepreneurship is an essential component of the study of business.

It will not come as a surprise that the expectations for Corporate Entrepreneurship are high. Yet, although some remarkable successes in creating new revenue and profit growth through Corporate Entrepreneurship have been achieved, the number of failures still appears to surpass the number of successes (Sykes). In fact, Corporate Entrepreneurship can be risky or even detrimental to a firm's short-term financial performance (Zahra & Covin).

What is Corporate Entrepreneurship?

It was Schumpeter, who defined the entrepreneur as anyone who helps move the economy forward by disrupting the equilibrium of the market through new combinations of resources. What all this amounts to, is that entrepreneurship can occur throughout large corporations involving any number of individuals. A scan of the literature on Corporate Entrepreneurship suggests that there are differences of views among researchers regarding the attributes that must be present for an organisation to qualify as entrepreneurial.

Corporate Entrepreneurship and Strategic Management:-

The strategy literature identifies three types of Corporate Entrepreneurship. One is the creation of new business within an existing organisation - corporate venturing or intrapreneurship as it is called (for example Burgelman, Kuratko et al., Guth & Ginsberg). Another is the more pervasive activity associated with the transformation or renewal of existing organisations (Stopford & Fuller). The third is where the enterprise changes the rules of competition for its industry in the manner suggested by Schumpeter and implied by Stevensen and Gumpert.

Changes in the pattern of resource deployment - new combinations of resources in Schumpeter's terms - transform the firm into something significantly different from what it was before - something 'new'. This transformation of the firm from the old to the new reflects entrepreneurial behaviour. Corporate venturing, or new business development within an existing

firm, is only one of the possible ways to achieve strategic renewal. Strategic renewal involves the creation of new wealth through new combinations of resources

Corporate Entrepreneurship and Organisational Types:-

The integration of Corporate Entrepreneurship and strategic management can be related to typologies of organisations and of strategic process proposed by Miles and Snow and Mintzberg, respectively (Burgelman, Veciana).

Miles and Snow have suggested four empirically-derived types of organisations: (1) “Defenders” have narrow product-market domains;(2) “Prospectors” search almost continually for new opportunities and experiment regularly with potential responses to emerging environmental trends. Their emphasis on innovation; (3) “Analyzers” typically operate in two types of product-market domains: one rapidly changing, the other relatively stable. Their top management must be capable of dealing with strategy in different modes and (4) “Reactors” that are unable to answer with effectiveness to environment alterations. They make changes just when are obligated. Mintzberg has proposed a typology of strategic processes which would seem to parallel Miles and Snow’s organisational typology.

A Framework for Mapping Corporate Entrepreneurship:-

Several studies have appeared to advance the development of a theory of corporate entrepreneurship. Zahra developed a model of corporate entrepreneurship based on environmental, strategic and organisational variables and empirically tested the model. Russell and Russell have also developed and tested a model of intrapreneurship based on environmental, structural, strategic, and cultural variables. Hornsby et al. have proved an interactive model of the decision to act intrapreneurially, which is focused on individual and organisational variables. Covin and Slevin analysed strategic and structural variables and tested the relationship between intrapreneuring and firm performance. In their model, Guth & Ginsberg identified five classes into Corporate Entrepreneurship:

(1) Environment Influences Corporate Entrepreneurship: In this category, Guth and Ginsberg included : (a) The impact of major environmental shifts, such as deregulation, can influence changes in strategy in a non-random way, with organisations (in the aggregate) moving away from one generic strategy towards other generic strategies; (b) The more dynamic and hostile the environment, the more firms will be entrepreneurial; (c) Industry structure effects opportunities for successful new product development. Clearly, changes in industry competitive structures and the technologies underlying them affect Corporate Entrepreneurship. Opportunities for new products and services stem from development of new technology and/or commercialisation of technologies developed by others.

(2) Strategic leaders Influence Corporate Entrepreneurship: Guth and Ginsberg included, here, the following factors: (a) The management style of top managers effects the level and performance of new corporate ventures; (b) Middle managers effectiveness at building coalitions among peers and higher-level managers in support of their entrepreneurial ideas effects the degree of success in their implementation; (c) Banks that are more innovative are managed by more highly educated teams, who are diverse with respect to their functional areas of expertise.

(3) Organisation Conduct/Form Influences Corporate Entrepreneurship: Guth and Ginsberg refer two factors : (a) Firms pursuing strategies of acquisitive growth have lower levels of R & D intensity than firms pursuing strategies of internal growth through innovation; (b) Creating new business venture units in larger organisations does not effect the level of sales from new products. Several researchers have noted a relationship between an organisation's formal strategy and innovation. Covin and Slevin state that mission strategies based upon building market share are more likely to incorporate entrepreneurial ventures based on innovation.

(4) Organisational Performance Influences Corporate Entrepreneurship: In this category, Guth and Ginsberg included : (a) Successful firms make more radical and more frequent product and process innovations than unsuccessful firms; (b) Organisations which experience

performance downturns tend to innovate new practices and change strategic directions only after prolonged decline leads to changes in top management.

AN INTEGRATING CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF CORPORATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP:-

The foregoing discussion has exposed a number of gaps in the existing knowledge about corporate entrepreneurship (Gautam & Verma). On the conceptual front, they find that there is a lack of integrative models. Moreover, there is not much clarity on the most few empirically - supported studies, but most of them concentrate on the individual characteristics of entrepreneurs. Not many have attempted to study macro-organisational behaviour. An analysis of the interplay between individual, organisational environmental factors is crucial for understanding the entrepreneurial process. Studies on entrepreneurial behaviour at the firm level will certainly be useful to better define the process and domain of Corporate Entrepreneurship.

Conclusions:-

The relationship between firm's external environment and Corporate Entrepreneurship activities has been the subject of interest in the literature (Zahra, Miller, Russel & Russel, Slevin & Covin, Veciana). Whereas there is consensus that external environment is a important antecedent of Corporate Entrepreneurship (Guth & Ginsberg, Gautam & Verma) there has been little empirical research on the patterns of the specific associations between these two variables. Also previous studies have focused on only a few environmental dimensions as the predictors of Corporate Entrepreneurship, offering only a fragmented view of their potential associations.

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